

FAST INTERNET, FAST GROWTH - FUELING UZBEKISTAN'S DEVELOPMENT IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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Annotation: *This article explores the pivotal role of increasing internet access and speed in driving Uzbekistan's economic and social development in the digital era. It examines how enhanced connectivity can boost education, e-commerce, healthcare, and innovation, while fostering a more inclusive society. By focusing on government initiatives,*

infrastructure improvements, and technological advancements, the piece highlights how fast and reliable internet is laying the foundation for a prosperous digital future for Uzbekistan.

Key words: *Digital era, internet speed, e-commerce, information technologies, innovation*

Introduction: The world is currently experiencing the Fourth Industrial Revolution, where managing information and data has become increasingly vital. Routine jobs are being automated through the implementation of advanced technologies, and even large factories are seeing a rise in remote-controlled machines and devices. For any country striving for development, creating the right conditions for professionals is essential. In this context, internet coverage and speed have become crucial elements for modern systems and economies as a whole.

In line with the *Uzbekistan 2030* strategy, outlined by the President of Uzbekistan on September 11, 2023, the country aims to position itself as an IT hub. Key objectives include increasing internet speed by tenfold, exporting IT products worth \$5 billion, expanding IT Park residents ten times over, raising the sector's contribution to GDP to 2.2%, and creating 100,000 new jobs in the sector, among other ambitious goals. In order to achieve the goals mentioned above, both the government and private sector are taking different but complementary actions [1].

Research&Methodologies

Mathematical and statistical methods are used, along with macroeconomic indicators and data, to conduct comparisons with other countries and regions worldwide. Additionally, conclusions are drawn by integrating research and theories from other authors to summarize and compare findings.

Findings

The access to high-speed internet plays a critical role in boosting productivity and driving economic advancement in any country.

High-speed internet allows for instant communication and seamless collaboration between individuals, businesses, and governments—locally and globally. Whether through email, video conferencing, or cloud-based platforms, real-time communication is essential for efficient decision-making, problem-solving, and coordination [2].

Companies can more easily collaborate with suppliers, customers, and partners worldwide. Cloud-based services and applications allow for sharing resources and data in real time, improving the speed and accuracy of operations. Faster internet speeds enable

governments to offer online services to citizens, such as e-governance, e-taxation, and digital healthcare, reducing administrative costs and increasing transparency [3].

Fast internet connectivity is essential for research and development (R&D) activities across industries. High-speed internet facilitates access to the latest scientific research, cutting-edge tools, and technologies that are necessary for innovation. With improved internet access, entrepreneurs can launch and scale tech startups more effectively. Access to global markets and digital tools accelerates innovation, leading to new products, services, and industries. A faster and more reliable internet allows individuals and organizations to tap into vast resources of information [4]. This includes educational materials, industry reports, and tutorials that help foster a culture of continuous learning and innovation.

One of the most significant ways that fast internet increases productivity is through the expansion of e-commerce and digital trade. Businesses, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), can reach global customers by establishing online stores, reducing barriers to entry in international markets. Fast internet enables consumers to quickly browse products, make online purchases, and access digital services, driving demand and boosting the economy. E-commerce platforms require fast, reliable internet to manage large-scale inventories, track shipments, and coordinate deliveries in real time. High-speed internet has a direct impact on the education sector, providing access to online learning platforms, virtual classrooms, and educational resources that help build a skilled workforce. High-speed internet allows educational institutions to offer courses remotely, expanding access to learning opportunities for people in remote or underserved areas. Students can access a broader range of courses and training materials, improving their employability. As businesses shift toward remote and hybrid work models, a reliable internet connection is essential for employees to perform their jobs effectively. It enables flexible working arrangements, reduces commute times, and improves work-life balance, leading to increased job satisfaction and productivity [5].

Sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, healthcare, and finance are being transformed by digital technologies that rely on fast internet. These industries benefit from real-time data analysis, automation, and machine-to-machine communication, which can drive efficiency and reduce costs. High-speed internet enables the use of Internet of Things (IoT) devices in manufacturing, allowing machines to communicate and share data for predictive maintenance, optimization of production lines, and supply chain management. In agriculture, high-speed internet allows farmers to use digital tools and sensors for precision farming, such as monitoring soil conditions, irrigation systems, and crop health in real time [6]. This leads to higher yields and reduced costs.

Fixed (wired) narrowband network	1,1	0,6	54,5	0,6	100	1	166,7	1,2	120,0
Fixed (wired) broadband network	2,4	0,3	12,5	1,2	400,0	1,8	150,0	3,6	200,0
Terrestrial fixed (wireless) broadband network	5,3	6,6	124,5	8,1	122,7	11,7	144,4	13,9	118,8
Satellite broadband network (via satellite communication)	0	4,9	n/a	5,1	104,1	3,6	70,6	3,3	91,7
Mobile broadband network using a portable device	68,2	84,2	123,5	86,1	102,3	78,3	90,9	85,7	109,5
Mobile broadband network using an integrated SIM card in a computer or USB modem	9,7	1,6	16,5	0,2	12,5	6,6	3300,0	6,7	101,5

Source: compiled by the authors [12]

As we can see from Table 1, we can compare internet access up to and including 2022. The following changes have been observed:

- Fixed (wired) narrowband network has increased by 20%.
- Fixed (wired) broadband network has increased by 100%.
- Terrestrial fixed (wireless) broadband network has increased by almost 19%.
- Satellite broadband network (via satellite communication) has decreased by almost 8%.
- Mobile broadband network using a portable device has increased by 9.5%.
- Mobile broadband network using an integrated SIM card in a computer or USB modem has increased by 1.5%.

The most efficient is the fixed broadband network, which has doubled in percentage. However, the number of households using it contributes only 1.2%, which is relatively low if society aims to achieve greater success in this area.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, improving internet access should be a priority, especially for landline fixed broadband networks, as they offer the most efficient and reliable connection. However, the relatively low household adoption rate indicates a need for further efforts to expand this technology. Additionally, satellite internet access, such as Starlink, presents a promising solution for bridging the digital divide, particularly in remote and underserved areas. To ensure greater success, society should invest in educating people about the benefits of reliable internet access, promote digital literacy, and encourage wider adoption of both fixed and satellite-based broadband services. By focusing on these key areas, we can work towards achieving more inclusive and equitable internet access for all. This ties everything together, emphasizing the importance of both landline and satellite options while also highlighting the need for education and outreach.

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